

The Role of Social Capital and Technology Adaptation: A Performance Study of Water Supply and Sanitation Managers

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to describe the role of social capital, technology adaptation, and the performance of group administrators at Kpspams in East Java Province. The location of this research was 170 Kpspams throughout the East Java region with reasonable functioning classifications. Kpspams in the East Java region was chosen as the research location because East Java is the province with the highest Kpspams functional status nationally. The time required to collect data is approximately 2 (two) months. The population in this study were Kpspams administrators throughout the East Java region who had an excellent functioning classification totaling 1016. The sampling technique used a probability sampling technique, a proportional random sampling method based on the same proportion for each group, so the sample determined in this study was 170 Kpspams members—East Java region. The research results show that the social capital variable was not able to significantly increase the value of each indicator of the management performance variable but technology adaptation has a significant positive effect on management performance as a consideration in improving management performance and sustainability of Kpspams in East Java Province. The contribution of this research is expected to be an input to overcome a problem that is being faced, especially in the aspect of program success at Kpspams in East Java Province and its development. The advice that can be given in this research is the development of several previous studies with distinctive characteristics not found in previous research, namely giving rise to a new dimension in the form of technological adaptation as a variable in the Kpspams research object.

KEYWORDS: Social Capital and Technology Adaptation, and Management Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

The drinking water and sanitation sector is a public service closely related to poverty alleviation. Good drinking water and sanitation will improve environmental quality and public health and increase community productivity (Yunasrun, 2013). One of the government's duties is to provide efficient access, adequate infrastructure, and utility services for the community. One of the central government's efforts in providing clean water is by implementing the Community-Based Drinking Water and Sanitation Provision (Kpspams) program, which is a supporting National Community Empowerment Program (PNPM) program to create clean and healthy living communities through the provision of community-based drinking water and sanitation services. The Kpspams program aims to increase access to drinking water services for underserved communities, including low-income communities in rural and peri-urban areas, as well as increase the application of clean and healthy living values and behavior in order to achieve drinking water

and sanitation sector targets through expanding community-based development approaches.

The government certainly wants the program to be developed and prosperous. Thus, one way for a company to achieve its goals is to improve the performance of its members. Performance is the result obtained by an organization, whether the organization is profit-oriented or non-profit-oriented, which is produced over some time (Fahmi, 2012). Group performance is the work result an individual achieves and adapts to the individual's role or task in a company or institution within a certain period. This is connected to a specific value measure of where the individual works (Motegi, 2015). Another definition of organizational performance, according to Rani and Mayasari (2016), is the quality and quantity of work results achieved by an employee in carrying out tasks according to the responsibilities given to him so that an organization can be said to be successful when the performance of the organization's members is high.

One of the factors that influence management performance is social capital. Putnam (1999) defines social capital as a feature of social organization, such as trust, norms, and networks that can increase the efficiency of society by facilitating coordinated action. Putnam (2000) said the social capital-based community development approach refers to the relationship between individuals, social networks, norms, and beliefs. He assumes that social networks have value and that social contacts influence individual and group productivity. Social capital is a series of relationships between people supported by networks, norms and social trust that enable efficient and effective coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit and good.

According to Eda (2010), the development of information technology for environmental sanitation and clean water is also needed to find new, more precise indicators and realistic monitoring and assessment. According to Aji (2005), information is processed data; its nature becomes other valuable data, usually called information. The definition of information technology, according to Sutabri (2014), is a technology used to process data, including processing, obtaining, compiling, storing, and manipulating data in various ways to produce quality information, namely information that is relevant, accurate and timely, which is used for purposes personal, business, and government and is strategic information for decision making. Development of a decision support system (DSS) that makes it possible to save energy costs by making performance-based and cost-oriented operational decisions. Reducing energy consumption in water system operations will be achieved by increasing the efficiency of the pumping system while ensuring optimal service levels. The application of technology in organizations can significantly impact effectiveness and efficiency and increase competitiveness. Information technology provides data regarding the organization's running so that organizations can obtain the data needed for making strategic decisions.

Based on the above mentioned phenomenon, this research aims to describe the role of social capital, technological adaptation, and the performance of group administrators at Kpspams in East Java Province. This research contributes to the development of several previous studies with distinctive characteristics not found in previous research, namely, giving rise to a new dimension in the form of technological adaptation as a variable in the Kpspams research object.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Fukuyama (1995:38) defines social capital as a series of informal values or norms shared among group members that enable cooperation among group members. Putnam (1993:132) states that social capital is an organizational feature of social issues such as reciprocity, networks, norms, social trust and group participation that can

facilitate coordination and cooperation for mutual benefit. Woolcock (1998) differentiates social capital into three forms: social bonding, bridging, and linking. Referring to Ridell (1997), community empowerment has five social capital parameters: reciprocity, trust in norms and networks, and group participation.

In Howard's (1986) opinion, adaptation is a process by a population or individual to environmental conditions, resulting in the population or individual surviving or being eliminated. According to O'Brien (2006), technology is a computer network comprising various information processing components that use hardware, software, data management and information network technology. A purposeful technological adaptation is needed to support business processes by applying technology and increasing connectivity between business processes. Technology cannot be separated from problems because technology was born and developed to solve the problems humans face. Limmie Chokchai (2007) states that technological adaptation is influenced by several indicators: high investment costs, funding sources, capabilities and expert staff.

Wirawan (2008) stated that "performance is the output produced by the functions or indicators of a job or profession within a certain time." Meanwhile, Colquitt et al. (2011) define performance as "a set of employee behaviors that contribute to achieving company goals." Based on the opinion above, employee performance results from the quality and quantity of work an employee achieves, which reflects how well the employee meets the requirements to achieve organizational or company goals. According to Robbins and Coulter (2016), performance indicators are a tool for measuring the extent of employee performance achievements. The following are several indicators for measuring employee performance: work quality, quantity, timeliness, effectiveness and independence.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Population and Sample

The population in this study were Kpspams administrators throughout the East Java region who had an excellent functioning classification totaling 1016. The sampling technique used a probability sampling technique using the proportional random sampling method, namely selecting samples based on the same proportions for each group or strata (Muhson, , 2015). So, the sample determined in this study was 170 Kpspams members in the East Java region.

3.2 Research Location

This research was located at 170 Kpspams throughout the East Java region, with reasonable functioning classifications. Kpspams in the East Java region was chosen as the research location because East Java is the province with

the highest Kpspams functional status nationally. The time required to collect data is approximately 2 (two) months.

3.3 Instrument Validity Test and Reliability Test

Validity shows how much this tool can measure what it wants to measure. Validity analysis uses Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) with a cut point of 0.50 (Ferdinand, 2006). A loading factor value greater than or equal to 0.50 is valid, and a value less than 0.50 is declared invalid, and the research indicator must be removed. Furthermore, the Reliability test is used to show the consistency of a measuring instrument in measuring a situation. A research instrument is declared reliable if the acceptable limit value for the level of reliability is construct reliability > 0.7 . Meanwhile, a reliability of 0.6 – 0.7 is still acceptable (Ghozali, 2015).

3.4 Data Collection Procedures

The primary data collection technique was carried out by distributing questionnaires via the Google Form application to administrators at 170 Kpspams throughout the East Java region with reasonable functioning classifications. This research used the questionnaire method to obtain information or data about the variables studied. The questionnaire, in the form of a list of statements, was distributed to management, and the questionnaires were used as research objects to determine the extent to which management performance mediates the influence of social capital and technological adaptation on group sustainability.

3.5 Research Analysis Techniques

The data analysis technique used in this research is descriptive analysis, namely descriptive empirical analysis of the information obtained to provide an overview/describe an event (who/what, when, where, how, how much) collected in the research. This data comes from the answers given by respondents to the items contained in the questionnaire. Next, the researcher will process the existing data by grouping and tabulating it, then taking the average (mean) and explaining.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

An overview of research data obtained from the results of respondents' answers, the data processing process and analysis of the data processing results will be presented in this section. The results of data processing will then be used as a basis for analysis and answering the research hypotheses that have been proposed. This research uses descriptive data analysis, which is then used to describe the condition of the respondents' answers to each variable. Descriptive data that describes the circumstances or conditions of respondents needs to be considered as additional information to understand the research results. The respondents in this study were 170 Kpspams throughout the East Java region, which had reasonable functioning classifications. Respondents in

this study were further broken down based on the chairman's gender, age and education.

Based on Gender, it is known from a total of 170 respondents that male respondents are the majority of respondents, namely 96.47% who participated in this research, and female respondents are a minority with 3.53%. Respondents Based on age, it shows that the respondents with the most significant percentage are aged between 36 years and 45 years, amounting to 42.9%. Moreover, respondents aged 18 to 25 were the fewest with 1.2%. Meanwhile, respondents based on education level showed that 46.47% of respondents had a high school education, meaning that most Kpspams heads had a high school education.

Social capital consists of 5 (five) indicators; each indicator has several questions in the questionnaire. Respondents' responses to the social capital variable show that descriptive calculations get an average score of 4.322, with the norm indicator with the highest respondent answer of 4.3735. Thus, respondents assess that the level of Social Capital in Kpspams East Java is very high.

Technology adaptation consists of 4 (four) indicators; each indicator has several questions in the questionnaire. Respondents' responses to the technology adaptation variable show that descriptive calculations get an average score of 4.146, with the expert indicator having the highest score of 4.2588. Thus, respondents considered that the level of technology adaptation at Kpspams was high.

Management performance consists of 5 (five) indicators; each indicator has several questions in the questionnaire. Respondents' responses to the management performance variable show that descriptive calculations get an average score of 4.179. The work quality indicator has the most significant average answer value, 4.2647. Thus, respondents assessed that the performance level of Kpspams administrators in East Java was high.

4.2 Discussion

Social capital refers to the favorable products of human interaction. Positive outcomes may be tangible or intangible, including assistance, helpful information, innovative ideas, and future opportunities for Kpspams. An individual does not own social capital but appears in the potential social network relationships between individuals. This can be used to describe the contribution to the success of Kpspams, which can be attributed to personal relationships and networks, both inside and outside the organization. Social capital can also describe personal relationships within an organization that help build trust and respect among administrators, thereby leading to improved performance.

The results of testing the first hypothesis, the influence of social capital on management performance (H1), produce a positive path regression with a path coefficient value of 0.191 and an insignificant probability with a value of 0.447, which states that each indicator of the social capital

variable is not able to increase its respective value significantly—indicators of management performance variables. In the confirmatory factor test, the social capital variable with each indicator and the management's performance with each indicator were proven convincingly as measures of this variable. So, the social capital variable and management performance illustrate the relationship between each indicator. However, in the Kpspams case study, social capital did not influence the performance of the Kpspams management.

The results of testing the first hypothesis showed that it was thought that the higher the level of social capital, the higher the management's performance, but this was not proven. This means that there is no conformity between the initial hypothesis and the hypothesis results from 170 existing Kpspams respondent data. It does not support Putnam's theory (2000), which views that social capital as one of the characteristics of community empowerment predicts or causes effective performance. Based on the results of this hypothesis, it can be concluded that the higher or lower level of social capital in the Kpspams in the East Java region does not have much influence on the high or low level of management performance in the Kpspams in the East Java region.

This research has the same positive and moderate influence hypothesis as research conducted by K. A. C. N. Perera and W. A. S. Weerakkody (2018), *The Impact of Human Capital and Social Capital on Employee Performance: A Study of Employees in Small Scale Industry Enterprises in Western Province of Sri Lanka*. Human resources and social capital are the most significant focus areas of future research studies. The main aim of this research is to find out whether human capital and social capital have a significant influence on employee performance. The research framework consists of two independent variables (Human Capital and Social Capital) and a dependent variable (employee performance).

Therefore, the aim of this research is hypothesis testing. The research was cross-sectional. This means it is collected only at one point for a specific period. This study measure maintained adequate validity and reliability. The sample for this research is employees in small-scale industrial companies in the western province of Sri Lanka. The structured questionnaire, consisting of 65 statements with a five-point Likert scale, was used to collect data. The sample consisted of 316 employees in small-scale companies in the western province. Therefore, the unit of analysis is at the individual level. Data analysis is conducted using univariate and multivariate analysis. Research finds a positive and robust impact of human resources on employee performance. Social capital also has a moderate positive impact on employee performance in small-scale industrial companies in Sri Lanka.

The variables in this research have been analyzed descriptively, model tested, and data analyzed and then interpreted further by connecting with theory and the results of empirical studies to prove the hypothesis formulated in this research. Technological adaptation is adapting oneself to specific situations to face a problem using the practical application of science. This self-adjustment can be done through the use of applications. The development of the times will change various things, so one effort to adapt to these changes is through technological adaptation. The existence of technology can make someone's work easier, especially the performance of Kpspams administrators.

The results of hypothesis testing, the influence of technology adaptation on management performance produces a positive path regression with an estimated value of 0.799 and a significant probability with a value of 0.000, which states that each indicator of the technology adaptation variable can increase the value of each indicator of the management performance variable. In the confirmatory factor test, the technology adaptation variable with its respective indicators and management performance were proven convincingly as measures of this variable so that the technology adaptation variable and management performance illustrate the relationship between each indicator.

The results of testing this hypothesis showed that it was thought that the higher the technological adaptation, the higher the performance of the management. This means conformity between the hypothesis and the existing data while strengthening the theory (Limmer Chokchai, 2007). Therefore, to improve management performance further, technological adaptation must also be increased.

The results of this research are the same as the results of research from Azhari, Nasrun, and Darwin (2023), *Work Ethic as a Dominant Variable in the Employee Performance Development Model on the Variables of Digital Adaptation, Organizational Commitment, Adversity Quotient, and Work Ethic*. This research aims to analyze the influence of digital adaptation and organizational commitment on employee Adversity Quotient, the influence of digital adaptation and organizational commitment on employee work ethic, the influence of digital adaptation, organizational commitment, Adversity Quotient and work ethic on employee performance. This research was conducted on educational staff at Medan State University, and 130 people were used as samples. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire with five answer choices. The instruments used were first tested on respondents outside the sample.

The research results show that digital adaptation has a direct positive effect on the performance of $\rho_{51}=0.155$. The results of this research are also the same as those of Sunny Ham, Woo Gon Kim, and Seung Hwan Jeong (2005). Effect of information technology on performance in upscale hotels. This research examines the influence of IT applications on

their performance in lodging operations. This survey was conducted in upscale hotels to identify the relationship between IT use and lodging operational performance. Front office applications, restaurant and banquet management systems, and guest-related interface applications significantly and positively impact performance; however, guest-facing interface applications are insignificant.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The test results show that social capital is not significant in management performance. The test results produce a positive path regression and an insignificant probability, which states that each indicator of the social capital variable cannot significantly increase the value of each indicator of the management performance variable. The test results produce a positive path regression, which states that each indicator of the technology adaptation variable can increase the value of each indicator of the management performance variable. The contribution of this research is expected to be an input to overcome a problem that is being faced, especially in the aspect of program success at Kpspams in East Java Province and its development. Based on the research that researchers have carried out, the advice that can be given is that similar research needs to be carried out in a broader range, both in terms of increasing the number and characteristics of variable relationships, populations, samples and the theoretical basis used in creating questionnaires. Further research must be carried out, especially to see the influence of other variables that can influence management performance and group sustainability apart from those studied because this research only found technological adaptation that can influence management performance and group sustainability. Furthermore, activities to build physical facilities and infrastructure, such as handing technology to community groups, should prioritize transferring knowledge and technology to administrators/managers to realize program sustainability.

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